

Virtual Screening Docking and ADMET Analysis of Small Molecules Targeting Thymidylate Synthase from *Trichinella spiralis*

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Abstract

Trichinella spiralis (*T. spiralis*), a parasitic nematode responsible for human trichinellosis, poses a significant global health threat. Thymidylate synthase (TS) plays a crucial role in DNA synthesis and repair, making it an attractive target for drug development against this parasite. In this research project, we aimed to identify potential small molecule inhibitors of TS in *T. spiralis* and evaluate their binding affinity through docking studies.

To achieve this, we first conducted a comprehensive *in silico* screening of chemical libraries to identify potential TS inhibitors using molecular docking simulations. Our analysis revealed a set of candidate small molecules with high binding affinities for *T. spiralis* TS. Subsequently, we performed extensive docking studies to investigate the binding interactions between these compounds and the active site of TS, providing insights into their potential mechanisms of action.

Our findings highlight several promising small molecules that exhibit strong binding interactions with *T. spiralis* TS, suggesting their potential as novel therapeutic agents against trichinellosis. These compounds offer new avenues for drug development and warrant further *in vitro* and *in vivo* validation studies to assess their efficacy and safety profiles. Ultimately, this research contributes to the ongoing efforts to combat *T. spiralis* infections and underscores the importance of targeting essential enzymes like TS as a strategy for parasite control.

Keywords: Virtual screening docking; ADMET Analysis; *Trichinella Spiralis*; Thymidylate Synthase; Rheediaxanthone B; PyRx Docking.

INTRODUCTION

Infection is characterized as "attack and increase of microorganisms in body tissues, which might be clinically in-apparent or bring about nearby cell injury on the grounds that of serious digestion, poisons, intracellular replication, or antigen-counter acting agent reaction". The irresistible process gives off an impression of being a coordinated series of occasions prompting host tissue annihilation and, in the event that not controlled, inevitable host annihilation [1].

The ancient idea of contagion (defined as the transmission of an infection from one individual to another—that is, direct transmission) was later reviewed as contagion between individuals that could be mediated by different means. This is called indirect transmission. This mediator could be the surrounding air (airborne transmission), a living being acting as vector (vector borne transmission) or even an inanimate object (vehicle borne) [2]. Many health and governmental organizations classify infectious diseases as either "directly" transmitted (e.g., through sexual contact, vertical transmission, or skin-to-skin contact) or "indirectly" transmitted (e.g., through airborne, vector-borne, vehicle-borne, waterborne, or foodborne routes). The categorization of directly transmitted diseases is particularly valuable in alerting healthcare professionals to potential infection risks, as these diseases are defined by direct person-to-person contact. This distinction serves as a practical guide for medical workers, indicating that they may face a risk of infection through direct contact with patients carrying bacteria that are transmitted in this manner. One more differentiation is in some cases made in light of the type of the transmission capability corresponding to thickness of tainted people, specifically recurrence subordinate versus thickness subordinate transmission [3].

Understanding the mode of infection is pivotal for implementing control measures and designing interventions to mitigate the spread of infectious agents. It is essential to recognize that the effectiveness of public health measures and therapeutic strategies hinges on a thorough comprehension of these modes of transmission.

Overview of *Trichinella spiralis*

The terms trichinellosis, trichinosis and trichiniasis all allude to a disease with the larval and grown-up phases of a parasitic nematode having a place with the variety *Trichinella*. The significant highlights of this disease are that it is zoonotic and that the infective hatchlings are meat borne (ordinarily pork, however progressively other creature meat). Exceptionally, the vertebrate host fills in as both a middle of the road and conclusive host for the parasite; a disease wherein both the duplicating grown-up worms and the infective hatchlings foster in a similar host. Various living systems including humans contract this infection by consuming muscle (meat) that isn't enough cooked. It is presently perceived that there are no less than eight *Trichinella* species, a significant number of which have as regular or supply has sylvatic creatures. People, then, may secure contamination from an assortment of meat sources, including, outstandingly ponies, wild game, birds, and even from reptile meat [4].

A comprehensive understanding of *T. spiralis* and its life cycle is vital for the development of effective preventive measures and treatments. The muscle hatchlings create from the infant

hatchlings, conveyed by females in the wake of mating in the host small digestive system of the grown-up structures, starting from consumed tainted meat. The larval development in the muscles is finished in somewhere around 20 days post disease. Its muscle hatchling lives in a changed piece of host's skeletal muscle cell, the medical caretaker cell, encompassed by a collagen container. The medical caretaker cell improvement, started by *T. spiralis* disease, is related with different changes, including cell-cycle reemergence and acceptance of DNA blend, trailed by the evident G2/M capture of the tainted cell in the cell cycle [6].

Thymidylate Synthase as a Drug Target

Thymidylate synthase (TS; EC 2.1.1.45) catalyzes the reductive methylation of deoxy uridine monophosphate (dUMP) by N5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate (meTHF) to create thymidylate (dTMP) and dihydrofolate [7]. Understanding the functional nature of nematode TS can be an exceptionally valuable instrument for developing novel medications for pathogenic species. As the response is the last step of the sole dTMP, which is fundamental for DNA combination, and furthermore for cell division and endurance, TS is a significant chemical objective in chemotherapy. A new related finding of potential importance is that TS seems to have an oncogene like function [12].

Given its indispensable function in nucleotide biosynthesis, TS has emerged as a promising drug target for various infectious diseases, including those caused by parasites like *T. spiralis*. In the current study the significance of TS as a drug target and its potential in developing novel drugs have been explored.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of Protein

The crystal structure of the drug target (PDB:5M4Z) from the Protein Data Bank was retrieved. The ligand in the protein structure was permanently removed prior to starting the virtual screening docking. In addition, polar hydrogens were incorporated into the protein structure and the atoms that make up the protein were given Kohn-Sham charges. Throughout the docking process, this phase is crucial because it ensures the accurate representation of electrostatic interactions. After this, all water molecules, co-crystallized ligands and typical protein structure artifacts were removed. Commonly, this method is used to speed up the docking process and simplify computing.

Selection of Lead Compounds & Construction of Small Molecule Libraries

Parasitic infections have long posed a significant threat to public health, and there are few effective treatments. It has long been recognized that the enzyme TS, which is involved in the nucleotide biosynthesis, could be a target for stopping parasitic growth. As a potential source for new antiparasitic targets, this enzyme, which involve intricate interactions, have been the subject of extensive research [8-10].

From the information collected 3 lead compounds with IUPAC names as 1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) pyrrolidin-2-one, 1-([2-(1-methyl-3-pyrrolidinyl)-1H-imidazol-4-yl]methyl)amino)-2-(5-methyl-2-thienyl)-1-ethanone) and Rheediaxanthone B was obtained. 3D structures of similar compounds from this lead compounds were retrieved using PubChem. Furthermore, the PubChem and Binding databases were searched for small molecule compounds that were structurally similar to the chosen lead compounds. Among these repositories, a significant number of hits—compounds conforming to Lipinski's rule of five and structurally similar to 3 lead compounds were retrieved in their 3-D format from the PubChem database.

Molecular Docking using PyRx

The virtual screening docking process was executed utilizing Autodock Vina integrated into PyRx. Autodock Vina is a generally used sub-atomic docking instrument utilized to foresee how ligands tie to receptors or proteins. The 3D designs of the selected libraries were acquired from PubChem in ".sdf" file and subsequently converted to ".pdbqt" format utilizing Open Babel, a coordinated part of the PyRx programming.

ADMET ANALYSIS

As shown by Kesharwani and partners in 2020 [11], anticipating ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion and Toxicology) properties for explicit lead compounds while growing new meds is a technique used to moderate potential unfriendly impacts related with medicines. This approach can reduce overall costs by eliminating molecules with inadequate ADMET properties from the drug development pipeline. Accordingly, in the current study, the primary ADMET characteristics for the highest-ranked compounds were assessed using the ADMETlab 2.0 web server, available at <https://admetmesh.scbdd.com/service/screening/index>. This platform represents an enhanced version of the widely used ADMETlab, primarily designed for a systematic examination of ADMET features. ADMETlab 2.0 is renowned for its efficiency in assessing pharmacokinetic and toxicological properties, offering valuable insights into the chemical composition and structural components of pharmaceutical substances. The top-rated lead compounds were entered into the ADMETlab 2.0 query bar using the standard Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System (SMILES) and the predicted ADMET properties were documented in the present study.

RESULTS

Docking scores are numerical values obtained from computational docking studies that predict how well a ligand (molecule) binds to its target protein. The larger the negative value i.e., higher the docking score, the stronger the predicted binding affinity between the ligand and the protein. In the present study, the top-ranked compounds from the "CID45242586" library exhibited binding energies ranging from "-8.2 to -6.6 kcal/mol" (Table 1a). Similarly, the top-ranked compounds identified in the other libraries, namely "1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) pyrrolidin-2-one" and "Rheediaxanthone B," demonstrated binding

energies within the ranges of "-9.4 to -7.4 kcal/mol" and "-10.2 to -8.2 kcal/mol," respectively (Table 1b and 1c).

Table 1a: Virtual Screening Docking of CID45242586 Library of Compounds towards *Trichinella spiralis* Thymidylate Synthase (PDB: 5M4Z)

Sl. No	Compound ID/Name	Binding Energy (kcal/mol)
1	28230373	-8.2
2	71797212	-8
3	97104814	-7.9
4	28360425	-7.8
5	31054613	-7.6
6	76533214	-7.5
7	129067958	-7.4
8	45179028	-7.3
9	45185893	-7.2
10	156276243	-7.1
11	45169323	-7
12	67962758	-6.9
13	57385834	-6.8
14	28230373	-6.7
15	71797212	-6.6

Table 1b: Virtual Screening Docking of 1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) pyrrolidin-2-one Library of Compounds towards *Trichinella spiralis* Thymidylate Synthase (PDB: 5M4Z)

Sl. No	Compound ID/Name	Binding Energy (kcal/mol)
1	7058166	-9.4
2	20056867	-9.2
3	46936402	-9.1
4	46937009	-8.9
5	25244665	-8.8
6	447090	-8.7
7	7058165	-8.6
8	12358859	-8.5
9	53840688	-8.4
10	25202302	-8.1
11	6602106	-8
12	167714	-7.9
13	21122964	-7.8
14	25774	-7.7
15	46936621	-7.4

Table 1c: Virtual Screening Docking of Rheediaxanthone B Library of Compounds towards *Trichinella spiralis* Thymidylate Synthase (PDB: 5M4Z)

Sl. No	Compound ID/Name	Binding Energy (kcal/mol)
1	73205	-10.2
2	10342859	-10
3	52951054	-9.9
4	195652	-9.8
5	11725803	-9.7
6	102060338	-9.5
7	10862711	-9.3
8	637252	-9.2
9	10342859	-9
10	15307925	-8.9
11	44233940	-8.8
12	7330544	-8.7
13	15560542	-8.6
14	44258380	-8.5
15	12136211	-8.2

ADMET parameters play a crucial role in assessing the pharmacokinetic and safety profiles of compounds, especially in the context of molecular docking studies. These parameters help in understanding how well a potential drug candidate is absorbed, distributed, metabolized, and eliminated within the body, as well as its potential toxicity. Incorporating ADMET analysis alongside molecular docking studies provides a comprehensive view of a compound's suitability for further development. Hence, in the current study, the primary ADMET characteristics for the top-ranked compounds were assessed using the ADMETlab 2.0 web server. Though, the analysis was performed for all the top 15 compounds, for clarity, the results of top 5 compounds alone representing each of the 3 libraries were presented here (Table 2a-2e).

Table 2a: ADMET Predictions – Absorption

Compound ID	Pgp-inh	Pgp-sub	HIA	F (20%)	F (30%)	Caco-2	MDCK
CID45242586 Lead Compounds							
28230373	0.006	0.471	0.003	0.988	0.867	-4.704	1.72E-05
71797212	0.002	0.006	0.875	0.974	0.927	-4.955	1.81E-05
97104814	0.003	0.016	0.889	0.971	0.681	-5.278	1.68E-05
28360425	0.003	0.001	0.689	0.986	0.985	-5.21	5.43E-05
31054613	0.12	0.51	0.006	0.949	0.204	-4.885	3.59E-05
1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) pyrrolidin-2-one Lead Compounds							
7058166	0	0.027	0.999	1	1	-6.625	0.000427
20056867	0	0.05	0.996	0.997	1	-6.524	0.000744
46936402	0	0.48	0.998	0.999	1	-6.564	0.000756
46937009	0	0.05	0.996	0.997	1	-6.524	0.000744
25244665	0	0.007	0.999	1	1	-6.519	0.000407
Rheediaxanthone B Lead Compounds							
73205	0.013	0.011	0.011	0.995	0.996	-4.965	8.48E-06
10342859	0.658	0.002	0.297	0.003	0.008	-5.054	1.61E-05
52951054	0.355	0.099	0.084	0.006	0.022	-4.85	1.06E-05
195652	0.015	0.071	0.038	0.007	0.002	-4.724	1.29E-05
11725803	0.013	0.011	0.011	0.995	0.996	-4.965	8.48E-06

- Pgp-inh: The inhibitor of P-glycoprotein, Pgp-sub: The substrate of P-glycoprotein. HIA: Human Intestinal Absorption, F (20%): Human Oral Bioavailability 20% & F (30%): Human Oral Bioavailability 30%. [Key: 0-0.3 – Excellent; 0.3-0.7 – Medium; 0.7-1.0 – Poor].

- Caco-2: Human Colon Adenocarcinoma Cell Lines [Key: ≥ 5.15 log cm/s – Excellent; Otherwise – Poor].
- MDCK: Madin–Darby Canine Kidney Cells [Key: $> 2 \times 10^{-6}$ cm/s – Excellent; Otherwise – Poor].

Table 2b: ADMET Predictions – Distribution

Compound ID	BBB	PPB	VDss	Fu
CID45242586 Lead Compounds				
28230373	0.906	96.46%	0.82	1.96%
71797212	0.914	79.69%	1.669	17.27%
97104814	0.613	81.43%	2.621	17.56%
28360425	0.092	54.91%	0.88	41.95%
31054613	0.666	91.57%	0.707	9.50%
1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)pyrrolidin-2-one Lead Compounds				
7058166	0.816	12.28%	0.294	77.85%
20056867	0.866	10.87%	0.311	79.44%
46936402	0.809	8.53%	0.301	79.47%
46937009	0.866	10.87%	0.311	79.44%
25244665	0.79	10.63%	0.321	78.74%
Rheediaxanthone B Lead Compounds				
73205	0.009	96.61%	0.633	3.90%
10342859	0.006	99.83%	0.388	1.96%
52951054	0.006	93.72%	0.843	9.33%
195652	0.011	95.37%	0.627	5.32%

11725803	0.009	96.61%	0.633	3.90%
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- BBB: Drugs that act in the CNS need to cross the blood–brain barrier (BBB) to reach their molecular target. [Key: 0-0.3 – Excellent; 0.3-0.7 – Medium; 0.7-1.0 – Poor].
- PPB: Plasma Protein Binding; A compound is considered to have a proper PPB if it has predicted value < 90 % and drugs with high protein-bound may have a low therapeutic index. [Key: ≤ 90% – Excellent; Otherwise – Poor].
- VD: Volume Distribution; An important parameter to describe the in vivo distribution for drugs [Key: 0.04-20 % – Excellent; Otherwise – Poor].
- Fu: The fraction unbound in plasma. Efficacy of a given drug may be affected by the degree to which it binds proteins within blood, as the more that is bound the less efficiently it can traverse cellular membranes or diffuse. [Key: > 20% – High Fu; 5-20% – Medium Fu; < 5% – Low Fu].

Table 2c: ADMET Predictions – Metabolism

Compound ID	CYP1A2 -inh	CYP1A2-sub	CYP2C19-inh	CYP2C19-sub	CYP2C9 -inh	CYP2C9 -sub	CYP2D6-inh	CYP2D6-sub	CYP3A4 -inh	CYP3A4 -sub
CID45242586 Lead Compounds										
28230373	0.515	0.71	0.925	0.402	0.831	0.096	0.425	0.158	0.893	0.712
71797212	0.512	0.693	0.166	0.518	0.169	0.588	0.295	0.765	0.342	0.85
97104814	0.754	0.557	0.49	0.068	0.386	0.534	0.751	0.458	0.541	0.312
28360425	0.958	0.455	0.962	0.083	0.937	0.576	0.869	0.234	0.916	0.454
31054613	0.696	0.584	0.912	0.6	0.623	0.448	0.172	0.154	0.764	0.549
1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) pyrrolidin-2-one Lead Compounds										
7058166	0	0.059	0.056	0.021	0.003	0.433	0.095	0.063	0.002	0.001
20056867	0.001	0.077	0.069	0.028	0.005	0.434	0.062	0.089	0.003	0.003

46936402	0	0.052	0.043	0.027	0.003	0.114	0.024	0.09	0.002	0.002
46937009	0.001	0.077	0.069	0.028	0.005	0.434	0.062	0.089	0.003	0.003
25244665	0	0.103	0.061	0.023	0.008	0.575	0.095	0.073	0.002	0.002
Rheediaxanthone B Lead Compounds										
73205	0.809	0.351	0.75	0.056	0.85	0.766	0.848	0.293	0.576	0.14
10342859	0.431	0.51	0.201	0.063	0.816	0.863	0.161	0.154	0.183	0.158
52951054	0.729	0.557	0.697	0.064	0.828	0.926	0.821	0.246	0.451	0.132
195652	0.282	0.137	0.541	0.062	0.724	0.927	0.07	0.26	0.163	0.142
11725803	0.809	0.351	0.75	0.056	0.85	0.766	0.848	0.293	0.576	0.14

- The human cytochrome P450 family (phase I enzymes) contains 57 isozymes and these isozymes metabolize approximately two-thirds of known drugs in human with 80% of this attribute to five isozymes – 1A2, 3A4, 2C9, 2C19 and 2D6. Most of these CYPs responsible for phase I reactions are concentrated in the liver.
- Result interpretation: Category 0: Non-substrate / Non-inhibitor; Category 1: substrate / inhibitor. The output value is the probability of being substrate / inhibitor, within the range of 0 to 1.

Table 2d: ADMET Predictions – Excretion

Compound ID	CL	T12
CID45242586 Lead Compounds		
28230373	5.291	0.063
71797212	4.913	0.649
97104814	3.869	0.475

28360425	8.3	0.438
31054613	5.916	0.1
1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)pyrrolidin-2-one Lead Compounds		
7058166	1.357	0.82
20056867	1.448	0.876
46936402	1.453	0.879
46937009	1.448	0.876
25244665	1.53	0.791
Rheediaxanthone B Lead Compounds		
73205	20.267	0.795
10342859	1.725	0.157
52951054	8.774	0.624
195652	4.937	0.448
11725803	20.267	0.795

- CL: Clearance of a drug is an important pharmacokinetic parameter that defines, together with the volume of distribution, the half-life, and thus the frequency of dosing of a drug. [Key: ≥ 5 – Excellent; < 5 – Poor].
- T1/2: The half-life of a drug is a hybrid concept that involves clearance and volume of distribution, and it is arguably more appropriate to have reliable estimates of these two properties instead.
- The output value is the probability of being T1/2+, within the range of 0 to 1. [Key: 0-0.3 – Excellent; 0.3-0.7 – Medium; 0.7-1.0 – Poor].

Table 2e: ADMET Predictions – Toxicology

Compound ID	ROA	FDAMDD	Skin Sen	Carcinogenicity	EC	EI	Respiratory
CID45242586 Lead Compounds							
28230373	0.901	0.908	0.057	0.665	0.003	0.021	0.954
71797212	0.07	0.94	0.1	0.037	0.003	0.007	0.761
97104814	0.199	0.974	0.094	0.027	0.003	0.006	0.826
28360425	0.325	0.908	0.478	0.032	0.003	0.015	0.677
31054613	0.94	0.944	0.231	0.08	0.003	0.024	0.748
1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) pyrrolidin-2-one Lead Compounds							
7058166	0.001	0.912	0.224	0.226	0.003	0.012	0.442
20056867	0.004	0.861	0.139	0.089	0.003	0.012	0.408
46936402	0.003	0.755	0.135	0.103	0.003	0.008	0.37
46937009	0.004	0.861	0.139	0.089	0.003	0.012	0.408
25244665	0.001	0.947	0.587	0.349	0.003	0.019	0.438
Rheedioxanthone B Lead Compounds							
73205	0.615	0.875	0.954	0.186	0.003	0.906	0.491
10342859	0.932	0.922	0.169	0.806	0.003	0.196	0.595
52951054	0.259	0.406	0.8	0.041	0.003	0.692	0.086
195652	0.899	0.094	0.68	0.266	0.003	0.032	0.024
11725803	0.615	0.875	0.954	0.186	0.003	0.906	0.491

- ROA (Rat Oral Acute Toxicity): Determination of acute toxicity in mammals (e.g. rats or mice) is one of the most important tasks for the safety evaluation of drug candidates.
- FDAMDD: The maximum recommended daily dose provides an estimate of the toxic dose threshold of chemicals in humans.
- Skin sensitization is a potential adverse effect for dermally applied products. The evaluation of whether a compound, that may encounter the skin, can induce allergic contact dermatitis is an important safety concern.

- Carcinogenicity is of great concern because of its serious effects on human health.
- Assessing the eye irritation/corrosion (EI/EC) potential of a chemical is a necessary component of risk assessment.
- Respiratory toxicity: Drug-induced respiratory toxicity is usually underdiagnosed because it may not have distinct early signs or symptoms in common medications and can occur with significant morbidity and mortality.
- [The output value is the probability of being toxic, within the range of 0 to 1. Key: 0-0.3 – Excellent; 0.3-0.7 – Medium; 0.7-1.0 – Poor].

Discussion

Virtual screening of three different compound libraries against *T. spiralis* Thymidylate Synthase revealed many compounds with remarkable binding energies measured in kcal/mol. Compounds from the CID45242586 library exhibited binding energies ranging from -6.7 to -8.2 kcal/mol, with compound 28230373 showing the strongest affinity. This potential drug can serve as leads for new drug development efforts. The compounds in the 1-(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl) pyrrolidin-2-one Lead Compounds library exhibited binding energies ranging from -7.4 to -9.4 kcal/mol, with compound 7058166 exhibiting the highest affinity. Different binding energies determine the ability of the library to contain compounds with different TS inhibitory effects. The rediaxanthone B library yielded compounds with binding energies ranging from -8.2 to -10.2 kcal/mol, with compound 73205 exhibiting the strongest interaction. This library contains an incredibly diverse collection of chemicals, making them interesting to explore further.

Absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicology (ADMET) predictions provide valuable insights into the pharmacokinetics and toxicology of lead compounds. Predicted absorption-related effects, such as Pgp-inh, Pgp-sub, HIA, and Caco-2 permeability, provide insight into the oral bioavailability and absorption potential of compounds. Distribution parameters like BBB permeability and plasma protein binding (PPB) provide information on the compounds' ability to cross the blood-brain barrier and their binding to plasma proteins, respectively. Metabolism provide predicted interactions with cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYP) and shed light on the metabolic fate of drug products, which is important for understanding potential interactions with other drugs. Excretion parameters Clearance (CL) and half-life (T_{1/2}) predictions provide insight into the elimination rate and persistence in the body of compounds, thereby contributing to their overall pharmacokinetic profiles. Toxicity predictors include skin irritation, carcinogenesis, eye irritation, and respiratory toxicity, providing a comprehensive understanding of the potential adverse effects of lead compounds. Top 5 compounds from each set of libraries were studied for ADMET and all had good values for each prediction.

The lead chemicals identified from the virtual screening and the corresponding ADMET predictions open the way for further investigation under different experimental conditions. Compounds exhibiting strong binding affinity and favorable pharmacokinetic profiles can undergo *in vitro* and *in vivo* validation studies to evaluate their efficacy, safety and potency as therapeutic agents against *T. spiralis*. While these methods provide valuable insights, it is

essential to acknowledge the limitations of virtual screening and *in silico* predictions. Therefore, experimental validation is crucial to confirm the actual inhibitory effects, pharmacokinetic properties and safety profiles of the lead compounds.

In conclusion, the combination of virtual screening and ADMET predictions facilitated the identification of small molecules that can inhibit *T. spiralis* Thymidylate synthase. The promising leads presented here provide a starting point for further R&D efforts in the search for an effective treatment against trichinellosis.

Conclusion

The research successfully identified potential small molecule inhibitors of thymidylate synthase from the specified compound libraries, including CID45242586, -(2-methylpropyl)-4-(5-thiophen-2-yl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)pyrrolidin-2-one and Rheediaxanthone B. The molecular docking studies conducted using PyRx provided valuable insights into the binding affinities and binding modes of the compounds with Thymidylate synthase. Based on the docking results, selected the top 15 ranked compounds with the highest binding affinity for further evaluation as potential inhibitors. The assessment of pharmacokinetic properties and toxicity using ADMET tools helps in identifying compounds with suitable profiles for drug development.

In conclusion, this research project demonstrates the effective use of computational methods, including molecular docking with PyRx and ADMET analysis, to identify potential thymidylate synthase inhibitors from diverse compound libraries. These findings provide a valuable starting point for further experimental studies and potential drug development efforts in the field of cancer therapy or related applications.

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